

STUDY OF EROSION WEAR OF ADVANCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectionally glass (GF), carbon (CF) and aramid fiber (AF) reinforced composites with Epoxy (EP) and Polyaryletherketone (PEEK) matrices were studied with respect to their erosive wear resistance against abrasive corundum particles and steel balls. Angular dependencies of erosion rates exhibited a maximum at 60° incidence. The composites could be ranked in GF/EP<CF/EP<CF/PEEK <AF/EP of increasing erosion resistance. The major anisotropy effect in erosion could be identified for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites in the different resistance to micro bending. For thermoset composites, erosion was facilitated by multiple matrix micro cracking and fiber-matrix debonding. For thermoplastic composites, higher matrix toughness allowed plastic deformation.

INTRODUCTION

The subject of erosion wear of advanced polymer composites has received substantial attention in the past decades. Interest in this area is commensurate with increasing utilization of composites in aerospace, transportation and process industries, where they can be subjected to multiple solid or liquid particle impact. Examples of these applications are pipelines carrying sand slurries in petroleum refining, helicopter rotor blades [1], pump impeller blades, high speed vehicles and aircrafts operating in desert environments, water turbines, aircraft engine blades [2], missile components, canopies, radomes, wind screens [3], and outer space applications [4]. Resistance to rain and sand erosion is called among the major issues in the defense applications of nonmetallic materials [3].

It is well known that the erosion wear of polymer composites is usually higher than the wear of neat polymers [5]. Different aspects of erosion behavior of composites are investigated in [6-8]. However, the comprehensive and systematic study of erosion in polymer composites has not been performed yet. There is no clear understanding of the mechanisms of erosion and how the properties of the constituents and the interface affect the erosion behavior of composites. Methods of predicting erosion behavior, based on the properties of components and the composites' microstructure have to be developed.

Unidirectionally reinforced fiber composites represent basic elements of a variety of complex composite structures. Therefore, study of their behavior is an important component of the analysis of erosion wear of polymer composites. The objective of this work was the experimental investigation of the erosion behavior of a number of advanced unidirectional polymer composites with thermoplastic and thermoset matrices under various conditions.

MATERIALS

Materials studied were unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composite (CF/EP; RIGIDITE 5212 epoxy prepreg system (BASF) reinforced with Celion G30-500 carbon fibers), glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin composite (GF/EP; RIGIDITE 5217 epoxy prepreg system (BASF)), carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composite (CF/PEEK; manufactured from the non-woven fabric NCS-1057 (BASF) made from the Celion G30-500 carbon fibers commingled with PEEK (150G) filaments), and carbon fiber reinforced PEKK composite (CF/PEKK; manufactured from the preconsolidated unidirectional tape reinforced with AS-4 carbon fibers (DuPont)). Some experiments were conducted on samples of unidirectional epoxy composite reinforced with aramid fibers (AF/EP; obtained from the Office National D'études et de Recherches Aérospatiales (ONERA, France)).

Results on fiber volume fractions evaluated by density method are in general agreement with suggested values by the manufacturers. The density method failed in case of AF/EP composite due to the intensive pull-out of fibers during cutting. It was impossible to completely eliminate the air bubbles at the edges of samples. This effect as well as the proximity of densities of Kevlar® fibers (1.44 g/cm^3) and epoxy resin made this method inappropriate for volume fraction evaluation.

Of each material panels of either 30x30 cm or 10x16 cm have been manufactured. The panels were cut to specimens of 4x4 cm in size.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two particle systems were used in the experiments, i.e., abrasive corundum particles and steel balls. The average diameter of particles in both systems was around 400 microns. Corundum particles were of angular shape whereas steel particles were round with a shape close to spherical. The Vickers hardness of corundum was by an order of magnitude higher than hardness of steel. At the same time, steel particles were almost twice as heavy as corundum particles. This implied higher energy of single impact by these particles.

A schematic of the apparatus used in the experimental study is shown in Figure 1. The particles are driven by a stationary pressure p and are accelerated passing the 8 cm long nozzle of 0.8 cm diameter.

Figure 1: Experimental set-up

The particle flow was characterized by the method of two rotating discs. Distributions of particle average velocities and mass flow throughout the flow cross section were obtained for several values of pressure p at variable distance from the nozzle tip. It was found that the average velocity at higher pressures is rather uniformly distributed within a 15 mm distance around the flow axis. However, the mass flow decreased substantially with the distance from the flow axis. A pressure of $p=8$ bar was used in erosion testing. The average velocity of corundum particles at this pressure at 16 cm from the nozzle tip was 85 m/sec.

Specimens were mounted in the specimen holder and covered by 2 mm thick steel plate with a hole of 30 mm in diameter. The specimen fixture allowed to vary a particle impingement angle.

The mounted specimens were subjected to the particle flow at a given impingement angle and angle of fiber orientation (Figure 2). Their weight was recorded as a function of erosion time. The mass of erodent crossing the circle of 30 mm in diameter, when oriented perpendicularly to the flow axis (normal incidence is denoted by 90° angle of impingement), was 15 g/s for corundum and 15.5 g/s for steel balls.

Figure 2: Definition of impact angle and fibre orientation

All five composites were tested under erosion by steel balls whereas only three composites were eroded by corundum particles, i.e., CF/EP, GF/EP, and CF/PEEK. Four impingement angles were used in the investigation, i.e. 90° , 60° , 30° , and 15° . For the CF/EP and AF/EP composites, an angle of 45° was additionally tested. Fiber orientations parallel and perpendicular to the plane formed by the particle flow axis and the normal to the specimen plane were studied. At least three specimens were tested for each set of variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Erosion rates

The erosion rates were evaluated as slopes of the linear part of the mass-time-plots. Angular dependencies for the erosion rate by abrasive corundum particles are shown in Figure 3. The effect of the impact angle on the erosion rate by steel balls is shown in Figures 4 and 5. The comparison of Figure 3 with Figures 4 and 5 shows that the absolute erosion rates of composites are 30 to 100 % higher when eroded by abrasive corundum particles.

It is usually believed that brittle materials exhibit a maximum erosion rate at normal incidence, whereas ductile materials show the maximum erosion at 30° . Following this classification, the behavior of both thermoset and thermoplastic composites under erosion by corundum and steel particles can be described as semi-ductile. The maximum erosion rate is observed at an angle of impingement of 60° for all materials but the AF/EP composite. The latter exhibit the maximum at 30° - 45° (Figure 5). In general, anisotropy of the erosion behavior is more pronounced when steel balls are used as erodent.

For higher incidences of 90° and 60° , the materials can be ranked in the following sequence characterized by increasing erosion resistance: GF/EP < CF/EP < CF/PEEK < CF/PEKK < AF/EP. At 30° , the erosion resistance of AF/EP composite becomes lower than the resistance of thermoplastic composites and comparable to the resistance of CF/EP composite under a steel particle flow. This effect is more pronounced for erosion perpendicular to the fiber orientation (Figure 5).

The comparison between the CF/EP and GF/EP composites shows that the erosion rates of the GF/EP composite are higher than those of the CF/EP composite for both particle systems and all samples and fiber orientations studied. The differences in the erosion behavior of these

composites should be attributed to the different fiber and/or interface properties.

Figure 3: Angular dependency of the erosion rates when impacted by corundum

Figure 4: Angular dependency of the erosion rates when impacted by steel balls

Figure 5: Angular dependency of the erosion rates when impacted by steel balls

The comparison of the thermoplastic composites shows a better erosion resistance of the CF/PEKK composite. Here, the difference can be attributed to more uniform fiber distribution in this material.

The analysis of experimental data presented above shows significant anisotropy of the erosion behavior of unidirectional reinforced composites under non-normal incidences. Anisotropy of the erosion was also observed by other investigators [1,5,8]. Usually, the erosion rate in orientations transverse to the fibers was higher than parallel to the fiber direction. Nevertheless, the mechanisms of anisotropic erosion are not fully understood.

Mechanisms

SEM investigation revealed that the erosion of brittle thermoset composites is a complex process involving matrix micro-cracking, fiber-matrix debonding, fiber breakage and material removal. The observed anisotropy of the erosion of these materials can be attributed to the following mechanisms. It is well known that the fibers in composites, subjected to particle flow, break in bending [1]. In case of an impact having a parallel component of the velocity with respect to the fiber orientation, bending requires particle indentation into the composite. The indentation involves compressive stresses and the resistance to microbending is very high. In case of a transverse particle impact, the resistance to a lateral component of the bending moment is lower and bundles of fibers get bent and broken easier. This facilitates increased erosive wear. On the other hand, the interfacial bonding between the fiber and matrix appears to be more resistant to a parallel particle flow. This can be explained by the lower overall strains in this case due to the higher stiffness of the composite in fiber direction and the higher resistance to indentation. The interfacial stresses are the superposition of shear and compression. In case of a transverse erosion, high interfacial tensile stresses are generated by the particle impacts. This causes intensive debonding and facilitates breakage of the fibers which are not supported by the matrix. Moreover, these broken fibers are easily removed due to a lack of adhesion. In case of the parallel erosion, the broken fiber fragments are often bonded to the matrix and can not be removed during a single particle impact.

Figure 6: wavy CF patterns on CF/PEEK after perpendicular particle impacts

Different morphologies of the eroded surfaces were observed for thermoplastic composites. A comparison shows a similar nature of the eroded surfaces of PEEK and PEKK composites. Most of the surface area is covered by matrix and exposes only a few fibers. Therefore, a good adhesion between the fibers and matrix is assumed for the thermoplastic composites. The surface texture appears rather isotropic on a large scale. Looking closer, however, illustrates that bundles of bended carbon fibers embedded in plastically deformed matrix are found when eroded by a transverse particle flow. This creates wavy fiber patterns (e.g. Figure 6). Some of the bended fibers are broken but not removed due to the good adhesion. The wavy fiber patterns can not be seen on the surfaces eroded in parallel direction. Here, many broken fiber fragments are mixed with the matrix microflake debris. The matrix debris can be attributed to a plastic matrix deformation and a damage along the spherulite boundaries [3,9].

According to SEM observations, the major mechanism of anisotropy in the steel ball erosion behavior for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites is the different resistance to microbending under the impact in orientations parallel and perpendicular to the fiber directions. In case of a parallel flow, bending is associated with an indentation and, therefore, is limited. A

transverse particle flow creates the lateral bending moment and the fibers are easier bent and broken. With brittle thermoset composites, the erosion is further facilitated by a multiple matrix microcracking and fiber-matrix debonding. For thermoplastic composites, the higher matrix toughness allows substantial plastic deformation which absorbs a great deal of the impact energy. This deformation takes place within a thin surface layer. The better adhesive strength of thermoplastic composites and the higher matrix toughness reduces the erosion rate.

Interaction of the Mechanisms of Anisotropic Erosion in Composites

Under the real conditions, neither the impingement angle nor the flow orientation with respect to the fiber direction remain constant. When an impingement angle or the flow direction changes, the mechanisms of erosion also change. This is manifested in the angular dependencies of the erosion rate and by the anisotropy of erosion. Here, the interaction of the mechanisms is studied for an anisotropic erosion under 60° incidence with interchanging orientation of particle flow with respect to the fiber direction.

In order to investigate the interaction of the mechanisms, one can rotate the specimen in the fixture during erosion and compare the resulting erosion rates with those at fixed orientations. In order to compare the major mechanisms only an interchange between the parallel and perpendicular flow was chosen. The angle of the fiber orientation with respect to impingement angle was incrementally changed in the sequence: 0°, 90°, 180°, 270°. The erosion time at each orientation was 10s.

Figure 7: Comparison of the different erosion conditions at 60° impact angle

Figure 8: Comparison of the different erosion conditions for CF/EP

Figure 7 shows the comparison of erosion rates for four materials under different erosion conditions. Wear rates under fixed parallel and transverse flow orientations with respect to the

fibers are compared to the average wear rate under incrementally changed orientation (interchange). Additionally, the average wear rate contributions during parallel and transverse segments of experiments with interchanged orientation are given. Figure 8 shows the similar comparisons for the CF/EP composite at 45° and 60° impingement angle. If there is no interaction between the mechanisms, one should expect that the wear rates during the parallel and transverse segments of the experiments with interchanged orientation to coincide within the experimental error with the erosion rates at fixed orientations. The analysis shows that this is the case for thermoplastic composites, indeed. This means that the mechanisms of anisotropic erosion for these materials are independent and an average erosion rate under changing conditions can be evaluated as simple superposition of the wear rates under fixed conditions. The results for thermoset composites are quite different. The average erosion rate under changing conditions is close to the maximum wear rate under fixed, transverse flow orientation. The average wear rates during the parallel and the transverse segments of the experiments with interchanged orientation are both higher than the corresponding erosion rates under the fixed conditions. This means that the damage mechanisms of thermoset composites interact effectively. The mechanism of interaction can be derived from the observed peculiarities of the matrix and the interface failure. As shown earlier, the dominating thermoset matrix related failure mechanism for transverse erosion is debonding due to the high tensile stresses caused by the lateral component of impact impulse. On the other hand, there is an evidence of the intensive matrix microcracking under the parallel erosion. The microcracks might be due to the high longitudinal tensile stresses under the particle impact parallel to the fibers. Therefore, the microcracks are parallel oriented to fibers and perpendicular to the interfacial cracks. Obviously, the two types of perpendicularly oriented microcracks can interact and by this increase the erosion rates. A similar interaction of the erosion mechanisms has been found for the CF/EP composite under 45° incidence. Therefore, the erosion of the thermoset composites at changing flow orientation is a complex process involving anisotropic fatigue and complicated interaction of microcracks. An average erosion rate under changing conditions can not be evaluated as simple superposition of the wear rates under fixed conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The angular dependency of the erosion rates of composites exhibited semi-ductile behavior with a maximum wear rate at 60° incidence. The erosive wear under a particle impingement perpendicular to the fiber orientation is higher than that under parallel direction. The anisotropy of the erosion is higher for steel balls than for the abrasive corundum and is most pronounced for 60° incidence. For the incidences of 90° and 60°, composites are ranked in the following sequence of increasing erosion resistance: GF/EP<CF/EP<CF/PEEK<CF/PEKK<AF/EP.

The major mechanism in the anisotropy of the erosion behavior for both thermoset and thermoplastic composites is caused by the different resistance to microbending under the impact in parallel and perpendicular direction with respect to the fiber orientation. In case of the parallel erosion, bending associated with indentation is limited. A transverse erosion causes a lateral bending moment and the fibers get easier bent and broken. For brittle thermoset composites, the erosion is further facilitated by a multiple matrix microcracking and the fiber-matrix debonding. For thermoplastic composites, the higher matrix toughness allows substantial plastic deformation which partially absorbs the impact energy. The wavy patterns of bent and broken fibers in plastically deformed matrix are characteristic features of the surfaces eroded in transverse direction. The better adhesive strength of the thermoplastic composites and the higher matrix toughness reduce the erosive wear rate.

The interaction of the mechanisms in anisotropic erosion is analyzed by experiments with interchanging fiber orientation. No interaction between the mechanisms is observed for thermoplastic composites. An average erosion rate under changing conditions can be evaluated as a simple superposition of the wear rates under fixed conditions. On the contrary, the interaction of the mechanisms accelerates the erosion for thermoset composites at changing flow orientations. The erosion behavior of the thermoset composites is a complex process involving anisotropic fatigue and complicated crack interaction. An average erosion rate under changing conditions can not be evaluated as a simple superposition of the wear rates under fixed conditions.

In general, it can be concluded that a conventional classification of the materials with respect to

their erosion behavior based on the angular dependency of the erosion rate does not reflect the peculiarities of the erosion in composites. For instance, both thermoset and thermoplastic composites in the present study exhibited a maximum erosive wear at 60° incidence which characterizes them as semi-ductile materials according to the conventional scheme. At the same time, the observed erosion mechanisms and their interaction at changing conditions is quite different for the thermoset and thermoplastic composites. This implies that another, improved classification scheme needs to be developed for the erosion behavior of composite materials. It can partly be based on the presence of interacting mechanisms in anisotropic erosion.

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